

ADDRESSING IN CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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ABSTRACT The article deals with the language is not only used for communication (think of thinking out loud, as in organizing one's thoughts), communication is one of the prime uses of language. And while communication is possible without language (think of gestures, signs, pictures, alarm sounds), language certainly facilitates communication, and arguably is necessary for the communication of complex content.

Keywords: communication, language, culture, address, conversation, speaker.

INTRODUCTION

Conversation takes place so frequently in social interactions that it is an important component of communicative competence. In principle, one cannot expect that the literal translation of the routine expressions of his own language into another will have the same effect in the target language. But in practice, the interference of one's mother tongue in using a foreign language seems to be inevitable for foreign language learner. An American scholar was greatly annoyed when addressed as Mr. instead of Professor by Russian speakers of English, who actually tried to show respect to him. A male Russian student in a university of the United States was also annoyed by the term "pet" directed to him from a cleaner. The student thought how that person could treat him as an animal, say, a dog or cat. He was quite unhappy until someone explained the good will of the cleaner towards her in using the term. There are more examples in actual interactions.

Since misunderstandings can easily occur, Helen Oatey [5, 13] suggests that "it is important to consider how addressing is conveyed in English and Russian, and

to what extent there are differences between the two cultures in this respect.” It is important to remember that the communication rules are culturally bound. This means that if you want to be successful in intercultural communication, you must know not only the rules of your culture but that of the culture of the person with whom you are interacting as well. Otherwise, you may interpret what you hear according to the rules of your native culture and misunderstand the speaker’s intension or even perceive insincerity or offence where none was meant. The key to clear the difficulty is to acquire adequate knowledge of, and to be willing to accept the cultural differences in communication. In this world with a diversity of cultures, no culture may necessarily be better or worse than another. Cultures are just different from one another. It is the cultural differences that make this world move, grow and enrich itself.

Based on studies by Rudkovskiy and Quirk [4, 12], there are six types of address forms: kinship terms, proper names, titles (occupational, official and social), pronouns, no-naming and others (terms of endearment and derogation, indefinite pronouns, nominal phrases and nominal clauses). Although the six categories of address forms exist in both languages, they vary greatly in contents and usage patterns. Besides, although social factors like age, kinship, acquaintances, generation, rank and setting and the principles governing politeness strategies are universal, the linguistic possibilities for the realization of politeness strategies are language specific, that is, different factor may carry different weight in the choice of address strategy in different languages. When comparing the two flow charts designed respectively by American linguist Ervin-Tripp [1, 104], it is not difficult to find that in Russian conversational system, order of seniority and age play an important part in their choice of proper address forms especially when addressing relatives, neighbours and seniors. However, in American English address system, seniority and age exert influence mainly on people of higher generation (15 years

older) in kinships, while first names instead of honorific titles can be used even when addressing older generations among friends and colleagues.

How to address people appropriately needs the taking of several factors into consideration, such as the social status or rank of the other, sex, age, family relationship, occupational hierarchy, transactional status, race or degree of intimacy. There do exist general rules of address forms in English, but because address forms are a social phenomenon, it varies on different occasions and the rules do not always take effect, just as Murphey T. said: "Personal address is a sociolinguistic subject par excellence. In every language and society, every time one person speaks to another, there is created a host of options centering around whether and how persons will be addressed, named, ... to those who interpret them, are systematic, not random. Such systematicity in language behavior, whether of use or interpretation, is universal, although what elements comprise the personal address system and what rules govern its deployment, vary across contexts. And such variation in structure is, according to the extant empirical literature, correlated with social ends and social contexts of language use. From this view, personal address is a systematic, variable, and social phenomenon, and these features of it make it a sociolinguistic variable, and social phenomenon, and these features of it make it a sociolinguistic variable of fundamental importance" [3, 130].

GENERAL RULES OF FORMS OF ADDRESS

Despite of its occasional inefficiency, we will first look at the general rules of address forms. An English or American person can be addressed by his name, his title his name plus his name, or by nothing at all, that is, no-naming form.

Examples:

(1) full name: *"A rise! David Johnson Black, do you know we are at war?"*

(2) first name: *"They are on your desk, David."*

(3) nickname: *"Jonny, there's something I have to tell you."*

(2) Title Examples

(1) title concerning family relationship: *"All right now, children! Outside for your walk, father's orders."*

(2) title of occupation: "Operator, could you please put through a call to Copenhagen?"

(3) title of rank: *"You are right, captain."*

(4) Honorifics: *"Your Royal Highness, twenty-four hours. They can't be blank."*

(5) other titles: *"Oh, darling." / "You dogs!" / "What do you want, fellow?"*

(6) Title plus name: *Doctor Smith.*

(7) No-naming: *"Good morning".*

These address forms can be found in daily communication, both in oral and written forms. In addition to causing other people's attention, address forms have other important social functions, such as to show respect, to show intimacy, to honor or to humiliate other people.

There are differences even in the way different regions in the United States use different forms of address. For example, the use of a person's first names in North America does not necessarily indicate friendship or power. First names are required among people who work closely together, even though they may not like each other at all. First names may even be used to refer to public figures, but contemptuously as well as admiring.

The various use of address forms sometimes merely serve as a marker of regional difference, but sometimes it is enough to cause miscommunication.

T. Lechner reported that the address form "Mr" has different meanings in the southern part of the United States than it has elsewhere. In the South, the term "Mr" is often used a substitution for the formula "I beg your pardon?" or "pardon?"

in asking someone to repeat what he has said or to explain something. The contrast in the use of the two forms is exemplified in the following conversation [2, 102].

(1) A: Could you tell me how late you're open this evening?

B: Mr?

A: Could you tell me how late you're open this evening?

B: Until six.

In addition, it was found that the phrase "Yes, Mr" is often used instead of "You're welcome" as a response to

"Thank you". For example:

(2) A: Could you tell me how late you're open this evening?

B: Until five-thirty.

A: Thank you very much.

B: Yes, Sir.

CONCLUSION

Summing up of all what has just been said we can conclude that one of the earliest sociolinguistic studies of speech behavior among speakers of English concerns the way people in the English speaking countries address one another. Forms of conversation are important for effective and successful communication and have long been considered a very salient indicator of status of relationships. One can use different forms of conversation to show his respects or fondness towards other people, or to insult or depreciate them.

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